

INTEGRATED MARKET COMMUNICATION FACTORS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF ONE SUB-DISTRICT, ONE PRODUCT ESTABLISHMENT IN THAILAND: THE CASE STUDY OF NAKHON PATHOM

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ABSTRACT

This research aims 1) to study the performance of one sub-district, one product establishment in Thailand, Case Study of Nakhon Pathom 2) to study demographic factors affecting the performance of one sub-district, one product in Thailand, Case study of Nakhon Pathom province and 3) to study integrated market communication factors on the performance of one establishment in one sub-district, one product in Thailand. The samples used in the research were SMEs, OTOP manufacturers, Nakhon Pathom province, 27 single manufacturers and cooperatives using multi-stage sampling methods. The analytical properties include frequency, percentage, average, standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis. For the results of the multi-regression analysis, it was found that integrated marketing communication factors influenced the performance of one subdivision, one product establishment. Nakhon Pathom province, including sales promotion, advertising, public relations, personal selling, direct marketing, and sponsorship, affect the performance of one establishment in one subdivision, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, sig value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 with a beta value of 0.451.

Keywords Integrated Marketing Communications, Performance Establishments, Establishments, One Tambon one product

INTRODUCTION

Past projects in one sub-district One Tambon One Product (OTOP) is a government-owned project that operates from 2003 to the present day, which aims to enable people or community members to use existing wisdom or local resources to develop into products and sell them to generate income for themselves. The results of the past performance can effectively generate income for local communities and people, as well as strengthen the foundation economy by government agencies to support knowledge. Technology, Capital, Management Link products from the community to the domestic and international markets from registering manufacturers, entrepreneurs. OTOP found that there are currently 87,468 OTOP operators and 186,356 products (Office of Local Wisdom and Community Enterprises, 2020). Product distribution channels of one sub-district project One Tambon One Product (OTOP) has 878 foundation economic promotion service centers, including 355 A-level foundation economic promotion service centers, 512 B-level foundation economic promotion service centers, and 11 C-level

foundation economic promotion service centers , respectively (Office of Local Wisdom and Community Enterprises, 2020).

With these changes, it has resulted in a pattern of marketing communications aimed at the group. Mass Marketing Communications has evolved into a communication model. Schultz (1993) focuses on integrated marketing communications that are more closely accessible to consumers, integrated marketing communications or IMC (Schultz, 1993). Affects the behavior of the target audience. Zinkhan and Watson (1996) have a similar opinion that integrated marketing communications coordinate all communication tools for branding, while Duncan and Moriarty (1997) have a similar view that integrated marketing communications are Communicate marketing that combines concepts and processes to generate the power of effective communication.

Marketing communication is a process created by a news source, namely a business, to convey marketing news to consumers, for the main purpose of which is to persuade to change consumption habits as the business expects, showing that marketing communication is an element of the marketing compound called promotion. (Malini Khamkhun and Teerapun Chokudomchai, 2019) and classified as a communication that creates a competitive advantage by considering the perception of communications related to the goods of one sub-district project. One product As a result of this problem, the researchers were interested in studying the integrated market communication factors on the performance of one sub-district, one product establishment in Nakhon Pathom, Thailand.

METHOD

Population and samples in research

The sample population in this research included 191 SMEs, 300 OTOP manufacturers, 136 single manufacturers, and six cooperatives. The samples used in the research were SMEs, OTOP manufacturers, Nakhon Pathom province, single manufacturers, and cooperatives of 270. Samples used in the study determine the total number of samples using the Taro Yamane formula at a confidence level of 95 percent, tolerances or errors of up to 5 percent, or at a significant level of 0.05 percent. Regarding to sampling in research, the principles of selecting samples to be represented in the study using the multi-stage sampling method are as follows:

Step 1: Use quota sampling. The method of comparing proportions based on the number of SMEs, OTOP manufacturers, Nakhon Pathom province, single manufacturers and cooperatives is divided into four categories: SMEs, OTOP manufacturers, Nakhon Pathom province, single manufacturers, and cooperatives to find samples.

Step 2: Select SMEs, OTOP manufacturers, Nakhon Pathom province, single manufacturers, and cooperatives from sample populations for ease of collection of faculty data. The researchers used convenience sampling in each category based on the number of quotas set.

Research Tools

Quantitative research is in the form of survey research, using questionnaires created from documented and related research as a tool to collect data and optimize the query's questions before storing the actual data, which divides the questions into three parts.

Part 1: General information of respondents includes gender, age, marital status, education level, occupation, monthly income, and cheek listing.

Part 2 Questions about integrated marketing communication factors include: Advertising, public relations, sales promotions, personal sales, direct marketing, sponsorship, events, marketing or special events are likert scale measurements, there are 5 levels, most, very, very, very, very, very,

Part 3 Questions about the performance of one establishment, one product sub district, Nakhon Pathom Province

The researchers took a questionnaire that was revised according to the recommendations of the qualified persons and tried it out with a group like a sample of 30 people and analyzed it for certainty by Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient method. Query accuracy value must be greater than 0.7 0. 3 persons then take the results to determine the consistency index value. (IOC: Index of item objective congruence) Integrated analysis of market communication factors on the performance of one sub-district, one product establishment in Thailand, Nakhon Pathom Province. Use multiple regression statistics at .05 statistical significance levels using multiple regression analysis statistics.

RESULTS

Integrated market communication factor analysis influences the performance of one establishment, one product subdivision, Nakhon Pathom province, using multiple regression analysis statistics.

Table 1: multiple regression analysis

	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	p-value
(Constant)	0. 693	0. 177		3. 923*	0. 000
Sales Promotion	0. 542	0. 082	0. 451	6. 628*	0. 000
Advertising	0. 338	0. 079	0. 336	4. 280*	0. 000
Public Relations	0. 503	0. 070	0. 512	7. 134*	0. 000
Personal Selling	0. 463	0. 075	0. 455	6. 184*	0. 000
Direct Marketing	0. 397	0. 082	0. 436	4. 863*	0. 000
Sponsorship	0. 426	0. 068	0. 498	6. 253*	0. 000
Events, marketing or special events	0.145	0.024	0.120	1.025	0.589
R ² = 0. 612, Std. Error = 0. 357, F change = 88. 263					

*Statistically significant at .05

According to a Table 1 study , results of analysis of integrated marketing communication factors influencing the performance of one establishment, one product subdivision, Nakhon Pathom province found that integrated marketing communication factors influencing the performance of one establishment, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, namely sales promotion, advertising, public relations, personal selling, direct marketing, and support for activities (Sponsorship), affecting the performance of one establishment, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, the sig value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, with a beta value of 0.451.

Sales promotion factors significantly affect the performance of one establishment in one sub-district, One Product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, sig value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, with a beta value of 0.542.

Advertising factors significantly affected the performance of one establishment in one subdivision, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, the sig value was 0.000, which is less than 0.05, with a beta value of 0.338.

Public relations factors significantly affect the performance of one establishment in one sub-district, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, sig value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 with a beta value of 0.503.

Personal Selling factors significantly affect the performance of one establishment in one sub district, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, sig value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, with a beta value of 0.436.

Direct marketing factors significantly affect the performance of one establishment in one subdivision, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significant at 0.05, sig value is 0.000, which is less than 0.05 with a beta value of 0.397.

Sponsorship factors significantly affected the performance of one establishment in one subdivision, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05, the sig value was 0.000, which is less than 0.05, with a beta value of 0.426.

Event Factors Marketing or special events do not affect the performance of one establishment, one subdivision, one product, Nakhon Pathom province.

The integrated market communication factor model influenced the performance of one establishment, one product subdivision, Nakhon Pathom province by 61.2% (R-Square = 0.612).

DISCUSSION

Promotional factors, advertising factors, and public relations factors are factors that affect the performance of one establishment in one subdivision, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, so entrepreneurs need to consider supporting the distribution of products into the market. Market logistics, which are activities related to the movement of inputs and the product from a source of factors. Production through the manufacturer's factory and then distributed to consumers. If OTOP operators understand the strategy of organizing and channeling, the

distribution will increase efficiency and potential in Market Trade Competition in the ASEAN and to study the needs of OTOP entrepreneurs to prepare and potential. In entering the AEC, most have a desire to increase their market potential. Marketing Promotion Advertising, with government or government agencies to help subsidize, will see the needs of these entrepreneurs as something that is important. Competition in the commercial arena due to cognition in terms of marketing planning, including building brands that are acceptable and in the minds of consumers. It is a variable that creates a strong, competitive advantage in business, although community business management is a matter for community leaders or group leaders to know how to manage the business.

The community needs to know what products can be sold and sustainable as a business. You need to know what products your leads need, and how the community can produce differently or better than competitors' products. How it also requires the ability to plan marketing promotions or communicate marketing by choosing tools to communicate marketing effectively and effectively to raise awareness. OTOP Branding Building trust, desire and deciding to buy OTOP products, as well as setting tactics for building brand loyalty. OTOP products, if analyzed in terms of properties The characteristics of OTOP products are products that are unique to each local community because of the raw materials, production methods, skills, craftsmanship that are the local wisdom of each community. It's a strong selling point to create a brand with a story, tell the target group to create a desire for the brand.

Personal Selling factors significantly affect the performance of one subdivision, one product, Nakhon Pathom province, statistically significantly at 0.05 in marketing, the strategy used is Customer Relationship Management (CRM), which is a strategy to build good relationships as a way for us to manage customers' sense of commitment to the product. Services or organizations do not think about changing their minds to have a stable customer base. To appreciate the status of engagement with customers requires observing the behavior of the customer. Then let's analyze the connection between customer behavior and marketing strategies. The CRM system's process starts with the collection of information about who the company's customers are, such as the customer's name. Information for customer contact, analyze the behavior of each customer, and divide them into groups based on the value they have to the company. Communicate with customers to learn customer needs and to satisfy customers in the long run, offering products or services that are suitable for each customer. Developed to attract customers, build relationships with customers, such as Websites Facebook Line, manage customer databases, data analytics, and provide customer contact channels. Can use CRM software to help with management.

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